

Re-evaluating the idea of Gestalt psychology for assessment theory in teacher education

Adam Attwood
Austin Peay State University, United States

Correspondence: attwooda@gmail.com

Copyright. 2021. Psychreg Journal of Psychology
Published by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

Educator preparation programmes (or EPPs) can apply a modification of a new Gestalt psychological approach to teacher education. If Gestalt is about patterns and recognition of the role of the patterns in how students learn, then teacher education in an EPP can emphasize the importance of interdisciplinary training in teacher education. Previous works have argued for the importance of fostering interdisciplinary teams for higher education. Gestalt psychology can be a part of the answer to the call for more interdisciplinary approaches to knowledge construction when considering the importance of identifying and evaluating patterns generally and within the context of assessment. Gestalt psychology itself has come in and out of fashion in the United States, for example, as its principles have been adapted and referred to by other names, not least of which was because of the increasingly complicated debates over behaviourist approaches to education. This paper adds to this discussion on the importance of interdisciplinarity for new approaches to Gestalt psychology as it might be applied to the teaching of interdisciplinary test design theory in an EPP.

Keywords: education; gestalt psychology; knowledge; principles; teacher education

Educator preparation programmes (or EPPs) can apply a modification of a new Gestalt psychological approach to teacher education. If Gestalt is about patterns and recognition of the role of the patterns in how students learn, then teacher education in an EPP can emphasize the importance of interdisciplinary training in teacher education. Roncaglia (2019) argued for the importance of fostering interdisciplinary teams for higher education can be important for accelerating student learning (Roncaglia, 2019). Also, according to Spelt et al. (2009), 'Interdisciplinarity can help to address today's complex issues since it is believed that a cross-disciplinary approach facilitates a comprehensive understanding' (p. 366). The emphasis on cross-disciplinary approaches over interdisciplinary approaches has occurred in a pattern over the decades (Newell, 1992). Meanwhile, Gestalt psychology itself has come in and out of fashion in the United States as its principles have been adapted and referred to by other names, not least of which was because of the increasingly complicated debates over behaviourist approaches to education (Abramson, 2013; Sokal, 1984; Wagemans et al., 2012). This paper adds to this discussion on the importance of interdisciplinarity for new approaches to Gestalt psychology as it might be applied to the study of the interdisciplinary teaching of test design theory in an EPP to emphasize problem-solving skills with the edTPA. In the United States, the edTPA (or educational Teacher Performance Assessment) is a standardised evaluation of preservice teacher performance in their full-time teaching internship. A teacher candidate's final edTPA is assessed by external evaluators. Passing the edTPA is one of the final steps in the teacher licensure process in the states that have the edTPA.

Gestalt psychology in context

The mention of Gestalt psychology might also evoke the context of behaviourist approaches to educational psychology that have been somewhat on the defensive in the past couple of decades (Wagemans et al., 2012). This is in part due to the ostensible popularity of constructivist approaches to differentiation that have partially eclipsed some of the strategies more firmly rooted in behaviourism. As Abramson (2013) observed, there has been a tendency to overemphasize the most recent research over the research from 25 years ago. However, as noted by Abramson, it is problematic to overemphasize recent research over older research in educational psychology because 'Such insistence will further detach the student from a body of literature, and a scientific perspective, that still has much to recommend it' (p. 67). Indeed, there is much scientific value in older behaviourist research studies and conceptual essays, not least of which are the principles of Gestalt psychology. For example, Gestalt principles can be applied in the design process of an interdisciplinary assessment involving the visual arts and social studies. Gestalt psychological theory should still have an important role in current discussions on assessment theory. Designing tests have roots in interdisciplinary approaches to determine student achievement. If student achievement at a point in time is foundational to K-12 test design, then tests can be aligned to standards-based models of assessment (Muñoz & Guskey, 2015). The question, then, is how do teachers encourage students to study for tests? This is, in part, a behaviourist issue in having effective stimuli to encourage students to want to prepare for tests. The factors that affect student motivation are interdisciplinary and, as such, the teaching of test design theory should likewise be interdisciplinary with the discussion of psychological concepts that have overlap with behaviourism.

Standardised testing in the context

Standardised testing may be defined as 'guessing games on the one hand and as definitive standards for educational excellence and accountability on the other' (Hopkins et al., 1985, p. 177). In this paper, the definition of testing methodology will be used in relation to what will be called 'modern standardised testing'—with a time frame limited to 1900 to the present. Modern test design procedures, as explained by Chappuis and Stiggins (2016), suggest that while formative and summative assessment is rooted in a standardized paradigm, assessment of learning should be systematically embedded in assessment *for* learning that is differentiated for the needs of specific learner profiles and learner groups to achieve proficiency goals. Nevertheless, there is a distinction between assessment for learning and evaluation of learning, and it is this distinction where tests become essential for objectivity in the evaluation of learning (Brown, 2019).

This review covers perspectives in the literature from 1923 to the present. The reason that articles before the personal computer age (post-1985) are cited is that a historical perspective is necessary by the precedent of several psychological researchers who cite sometimes decades-old studies in the introductory paragraphs of their primary studies and textbooks (Hopkins et al., 1985; Forbes & Cottle, 1953; Gettinger & White, 1979; Petrosko, 1978; Rocklin & O'Donnell, 1987; Sackett et al., 2009). Older studies still have considerable value when discussing assessment theory, especially when considering the importance of patterns in determining when the curriculum should be modified.

What is the correlation of modern standardised testing (also known as standardised achievement testing) vis-à-vis non-standardised or 'self-adapted testing' in assessing students' cognition? Gestalt psychological principles can provide an answer. In other words, when a pattern of scores is evaluated, then a pattern (or lack

thereof) can provide an answer to how instruction might be modified based on the identification of where test-takers score in any given standardised assessment.

The issue of concurrent validity coefficients is important for the discussion of testing methodology as it relates to underlying student cognition because this factor seems to support standardised testing as a valid assessment tool (Hopkins et al., 1985). According to Hopkins et al. (1985), there has been a relatively strong correlation between standardised test scores and student ranks based on teacher judgments. Based on their sample, only the reading subtest score did not closely correlate test score with teachers' assessment of students' class rank based on grades. A study from a century ago conducted by Wallin (1923) suggested that teachers' judgments vis-à-vis standardised testing results have long correlated with some types of group tests suggesting the validity and reliability of standardised tests. Unlike Hopkins et al. (1985), Wallin (1923) considered standardised tests to be less than always reliable because the teacher-standardised test correlation depended on the type of test used for the context. The Binet and Myers tests, for example, rate students 'most accurately, while the Detroit is decidedly the most inaccurate, and 'the teacher's judgement is superior to the Pressey and Detroit.' The exact nuances of the tests noted by Wallin (1923) are not necessary for this paper except to say that they have a likeness to the more recent Direct Instruction model. In other words, the various standardised tests of the first half of the twentieth century were considered a reliable measure to evaluate student learning, and such standardised tests faced little contemporary criticism. Wallin (1923) even went so far as to declare those correlations are 'fictitiously high' with the Binet test because it tends to rate students higher than 'group tests' (p. 236). The top and bottom quartile do tend to align in standardised test-taking ability at nearly every level because the majority of student's scores polarize (Wallin, 1923, p. 240-241). Hopkins et al. (1985) surveyed tests across five disciplines and thus their research appears more broadly based than Wallin's sample-based on subjects alone. But Wallin (1923) noted more testing types; therefore, the comparison between the 1923 study with the one published in 1985 suggest notable correlations for the concurrent validity of standardised testing in general.

The most recent study of standardised testing and their predictive capacities of student academic achievement seem to support the validity of standardised testing with relatively few outside variables. Sackett et al. (2009) concluded that the meta-analytic mean in their study suggested a close correlation of test score to course grade – even when controlling for socioeconomic factors, which only changes the 'meta-analytic mean test-grade correlation' by a statistically negligible amount (p. 17). Earlier research suggested other factors. For example, the literacy question was posited by researchers regarding the role of students' comprehension of written instructions on subtests. Test scores may be based on the issue of the students' reading ability. Forbes and Cottle (1953) concluded that 'standardised tests were easily within the range of reading difficulty of those for whom the tests were designed' (p. 190). Rodríguez Bou and Stovall (1950) asserted that 'standardised objective tests of various kinds should be utilized as a screening device' for several reasons not least of which is 'reading proficiency' (p. 319). The non-standardised assessment had created chaotic college admissions screening because a top grade at one school may not have equated to the quality that a top grade another school indicated (Rodríguez Bou & Stovall, 1950, p. 317). With this background, the movement for mass standardization may be seen in its infancy.

According to Hopkins et al. (1985), 'in general, standardised achievement tests have substantial validity' or assessing student cognition because the data support that 'students are attaining the curricular objectives and skills' in correlation with teacher evaluations (p. 181). However, in a more recent study, Rocklin et al., (1995) note that the data from their experiments suggest that individualized self-adapted testing significantly lessened student anxiety. Therefore, students' self-concept of cognitive ability increased when the test was individualized. Self-adapted testing specifically increased students' estimated ability because they attempted to answer more questions than they did on the standardised test (Rocklin et al., 1995, p. 107). Butterfield and Belmont (1971) note that 'recall speed varies with the presentation position' of multiple-choice test items (p. 320). This suggests that standardised tests do not necessarily assess student's academic long-term knowledge, but rather, their ability to recognise patterns that improve their knowledge recall short-term. This is an important skill to be sure, but if modern standardised tests are supposed to quantifiably assess general academic achievement, then short-term recall alone is not enough. Self-adapted testing may solve this issue because the research suggests that individualised tests align with students' particular subject interests more directly. Rocklin and O'Donnell (1987) note that each of the participants who took the self-adapted test could select the items to answer and, thus, were less anxious. Their 'higher estimates of ability were not attributable to students' choice of items' because the 'students who took the self-adapted test chose items indistinguishable in difficulty from those chosen by students who took the hard test' (Rocklin & O' Donnell, 1987, p. 318). This may counter the suggestion of Butterfield and Belmont (1971) and Butterfield et al. (1971) because self-adapted testing appears to correspond more closely with long-term and short-term recall simultaneously, while standardised testing creates a focus only on short-term recall.

Standardised tests as tools for formative assessment

A lower level of anxiety triggered by the individualised testing model allows for greater student achievement across subjects. Perhaps the most significant of the data from Lang et al. (2008) is the correlation between math scores and adapted testing conditions. The adaptive testing model “had an overall positive impact on students’ mathematics scores. The students who took the standardised test had an aggregate math achievement score of 656.28 while the students who took the self-adapted test had a score of 668.56 (Lang et al., 2008, p. 116). Gettinger and White (1979) examined mathematics concepts and computation within the context of ‘time to learn’ or TTL, which is defined as allowing students more time to complete a test based on the empirical data of the number of trials to criterion on single units of material. This was correlated with standardised test scores. The results were promising for student performance when more time was allowed to take the standardised test. Petrosko (1978) observed in a study of mathematics tests that the standardised items did not necessarily correlate with higher student achievement. An irony may exist in Petrosko’s (1978) study that mathematics test authors did not adhere to concurrent and predictive validity. Instead, according to Petrosko (1978), the standardised test in Mathematics that was observed in that case study sometimes veered away from the educational objective of the test. If the test authors do not agree on how best to standardize then self-adapted testing seems the logical alternative.

There does not need to be an either-or dichotomy. Standardised tests are not the problem *per se*, but rather, the components of the tests – such as the time allowed for students to take the tests—need periodic review. Such reviews are similar to a combinational form of standardised testing and self-adapted testing. According to Gettinger and White (1979), ‘These data support the notion of individual differences in rates of learning,’ (p. 405) and predictive conclusions may be correlated with standardised tests scores. Time to learn (or TTL) methodology has shown a high correlation with achievement scores because tests may be administered to students who need 2 or 3 times more time to demonstrate mastery. Lang et al. (2008) approached the issue of student cognition vis-à-vis self-adapted testing from a different angle. The results of their study indicated that ‘testing accommodations appeared to have a positive effect [in] both reading and math,’ and the students had ‘positive perceptions of testing accommodations’ (Lang et al., 2008, p. 115). Self-adapted testing, in other words, tended to be perceived as a beneficial concept by both groups of students in the study control groups. Self-adapted testing is a component of formative assessment rather than high-stakes summative evaluation. As Brown (2019) noted, assessment for learning (or *AfL*) helps to foster an environment of learning, ‘However, it [*AfL*] does so by being a curricular and pedagogical practice, not an assessment process’ (p. 6). The implication being that evaluation of learning should be as much of an objective measure based on the learning targets and standards as possible, though getting to that point can and in many ways should be through formative assessment for learning that has objective evaluations along the way.

Ultimately, standardised testing has been supported by some research because of its correlation to student academic achievement *patterns* (Hopkins et al., 1985; Sackett et al., 2009). However, other research has suggested negative conclusions regarding standardised testing as a measurement of students’ applied cognition or long-term academic achievement also based on apparent patterns (Lang et al., 2008; Rocklin et al., 1995; Rocklin & O’Donnell, 1987). And other research has suggested inconclusive results that may or may not correlate high academic achievement with high standardised test scores. The correlations may depend on how the test was customized – perhaps an irony that raises questions about standardised testing as a predictive indicator of achievement (Butterfield & Belmont, 1971; Butterfield et al., 1971; Petrosko, 1978; Rocklin & O’Donnell, 1987; Wallin, 1923).

Assessment and the edTPA rubrics in the US

The edTPA Task 3 ‘Assessing Student Learning’ emphasises formative and summative assessment skills of teacher candidates. Designed by the Stanford Center for Assessment, Learning, and Equity (2019), the Task 3 rubrics include Rubric 11 (‘Analysis of Student Learning’), Rubric 12 (‘Providing Feedback to Guide Further Learning’), Rubric 13 (‘Student Use of Feedback’), Rubric 14 (‘Analyzing Students’ Language Use and Literacy Learning’), and Rubric 15 (‘Using Assessment to Inform Instruction’). With five of the fifteen edTPA rubrics focused on assessment, teacher candidates must receive substantial instruction in assessment design in their EPP through an assessment course. When reading the edTPA rubrics, there appears to be support for formative assessment and teacher reflection on how the assessment may inform their teaching and assessment design practice. Considering the encouragement of both formative and summative assessment that is both *of* learning and *for* learning, the next item to address may be the design of teaching assessment theory and practice to preservice teachers. Assessment is a process that builds on preceding instructional units, and the edTPA

suggests the importance of backwards-design so that instruction directly links to the assessment of and for student learning to form a positive instructional and learning loop for both the students and the teacher in which both inform each other for mutual growth. These rubrics further provide support for standards-based grading in that the goal of formative assessment is, in one interpretation, to ideally get all students to achieve proficiency in meeting the learning targets. Standards-based grading is not antithetical to Gestalt psychological principles or even to behaviourism broadly speaking, as part of the goal of standards-based grading is for achieving proficiency of all learning targets. Rubrics 11-13 are essentially observing student response to the formative assessment (stimuli) and adjusting accordingly to help ensure that students achieve proficiency on the summative assessment.

CONCLUSION

Summative tests tend to emphasize knowledge learning targets, but tests can also assess for reasoning, too. There can be an emphasis on problem-solving in formative and summative tests. The edTPA Rubrics 11-15 motivate to design formative elements as part of summative assessments. The patterns, or Gestalts, that might be identified through analysis of data from standardised tests over time can be correlated with individual classroom assessments as long as both instruments remain unchanged for enough time so that data can be collected over years to reliably identify any patterns. Perhaps ideally, if standardised tests would remain unchanged for at least five years and classroom assessments were consistent during that time, far more could be determined by a Gestalt analysis of the data of those test scores within any given content area across at least five years. Nevertheless, even with tests modified every couple of years, there is substantially important data that is gathered. Interdisciplinary collaboration would benefit test design and the analysis of test data for the teaching of test construction for maximizing the reliability of tests for measuring student achievement and for how those results can then inform instruction. With consistent test data then, perhaps the potential benefits of Gestalt psychology about a potential collaboration with behaviourist theories of education could be re-evaluated for greater inclusion in educator preparation programmes.

REFERENCES

- Abramson, C. (2013). Problems of teaching the behaviorist perspective in the cognitive revolution. *Behavioral Sciences*, 3(1), 55–71. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs3010055>
- Brown, G. T. L. (2019). Is assessment for learning really assessment? *Frontiers in Education*, 4(64), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2019.00064>
- Butterfield, E. C., & Belmont, J. M. (1971). Relations of storage and retrieval strategies as short-term memory processes. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 89(2), 319–328. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0031191>
- Butterfield, E. C., Belmont, J. M., & Peltzman, D. J. (1971). Effects of recall requirement on acquisition strategy. *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 90(2), 347–348. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0031554>
- Chappuis, J., & Stiggins, R. J. (2016). *An introduction to student-involved assessment for learning* (7th ed.). Pearson.
- Forbes, F. W. & Cottle, W. C. (1953). A new method for determining readability of standardized tests. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 37(3), 185–190. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0061975>
- Gettinger, M. & White, M. A. (1979). Which is the stronger correlate of school learning? Time to learn or measured intelligence? *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 71(4), 405–412. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.71.4.405>
- Hopkins, K. D., George, C. A., & Williams, D. D. (1985). The concurrent validity of standardized achievement tests by content area using teachers' ratings as criteria. *Journal of Educational Measurement*, 22(3), 177–182. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-3984.1985.tb01056.x>
- Lang, S. C., Elliott, S. N., Bolt, D. M., & Kratochwill, T. R. (2008). The effects of testing accommodations on students' performances and reactions to testing. *School Psychology Quarterly*, 23(1), 107–124. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1045-3830.23.1.107>
- Muñoz, M. A., & Guskey, T. R. (2015). Standards-based grading and reporting will improve education. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 96(7), 64–68. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0031721715579043>
- Newell, W. H. (1992). Academic disciplines and undergraduate interdisciplinary education: Lessons from the School of Interdisciplinary Studies at Miami University, Ohio. *European Journal of Education*, 27(3), 211–221. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1503450>
- Petrosko, J. M. (1978). The quality of standardized high school mathematics tests. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 9(2), 137–148. <https://doi.org/10.5951/jresmetheduc.9.2.0137>

- Rocklin, T., & O' Donnell, A. M. (1987). Self-adapted testing: A performance-improving variant of computerized adaptive testing. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 79(3), 315–319. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.79.3.315>
- Rocklin, T. R., O' Donnell, A. M., & Holst, P. M. (1995). Effects and underlying mechanisms of self-adapted testing. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 87(1), 103–116. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.87.1.103>
- Rodríguez Bou, I., & Stovall, F. L. (1950). A study of high-school academic indices as a criterion for college admission. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 41(5), 309–320. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0063455>
- Roncaglia, I. (2019). Building bridges not silos: Accessible theoretical knowledge that continues to inform practice. *Psychreg Journal of Psychology*, 3(1), 52–57. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3236687>
- Sackett, P. R., Kuncel, N. R., Arneson, J. J., Cooper, S. R., & Waters, S. D. (2009). Does socioeconomic status explain the relationship between admissions tests and post-secondary academic performance? *Psychological Bulletin*, 135(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0013978>
- Sokal, M. M. (1984). The Gestalt psychologists in behaviorist America. *The American Historical Review*, 89(5), 1240–1263. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1867042>
- Spelt, E. J. H., Biemans, H. J. A., Tobi, H., Luning, P. A., & Mulder, M. (2009). Teaching and learning in interdisciplinary higher education: A systematic review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 21, 365–378. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-009-9113-z>
- Wallin, J. E. W. (1923). The consistency shown by intelligence ratings based on standardized tests and teachers' estimates. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 14(4), 231–246. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0072342>
- Wagemans, J., Elder, J. H., Kubovy, M., Palmer, S. E., Peterson, M. A., Singh, M., & von der Heydt, R. (2012). A century of Gestalt psychology in visual perception: I. Perceptual grouping and figure-ground organization. *Psychological Bulletin*, 138(6), 1172–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0029333>